

ESSENTIAL AMENDMENT TO THE R SCRIPT

in the Electronic supplementary material of

Sigovini M., Keppel E., Tagliapietra D. (2013) *M-AMBI revisited: looking inside a widely-used benthic index*. *Hydrobiologia* 717: 41-50. DOI 10.1007/s10750-013-1565-y

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After the paper was published, there have been a major change in the function "factor.scores" in psych package. This cause the published version of the script to give wrong results. You may easily correct the script by yourself by changing the following rows:

```
METRICS.scores <- factor.scores(METRICS.tot, f = METRICS.fa, method = c("components"))$scores  
# METRICS.scores <- scale(METRICS.tot) %*% METRICS.fa$loadings
```

in this way:

```
#METRICS.scores <- factor.scores(METRICS.tot, f = METRICS.fa, method = c("components"))$scores  
METRICS.scores <- scale(METRICS.tot) %*% METRICS.fa$loadings
```

i.e. switch the two command lines.